

Studies On The "Chinese Discourse" Of Chinese Piano Music

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 14, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 15, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Chinese Discourse, Piano Music</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7641550</p>	<p><i>In recent years, how to construct the discourse system of music theory with Chinese characteristics has attracted more and more attention from academic circles. People with insight into the field of language, culture, and art circles have paid close attention to Chinese discourse research, established research bases, organized academic seminars, and published several academic papers and works, which have accumulated fruitful research results for the construction of the music theory discourse system with Chinese characteristics, which can be described as "overwhelming". Not only because of dozens of works and nearly a thousand journals and master and doctoral papers, but more importantly, its huge research system, interdisciplinary disciplines, rich research content, and in-depth analysis and discussion, the research results show great diversity and openness. In particular, those research results combined with traditional aesthetics, culture, hermeneutics, and other disciplines are more diverse from various angles and have unique insights. Such diverse and rich theoretical research results provide a great extension space for the research of this paper.</i></p>

Introduction

After sorting out and researching, the paper divides the relevant research results into the following six fields (see Table 1).

Table 1 Areas involved in the research results

field of investigation	Sinicism	Traditional aesthetics	Traditional music	create	give an instrumental performance	Word building
Number of papers	349	202	171	92 (70+22)	70 (36+34)	58 (52+6)
% amount to	37%	21%	18%	10.4%	8.1%	5.5%
About 942 articles						

Source: collation of this study

By entering two etymology of "Chinese piano music" and "Chinese" style, The data of 349 journals and master and doctoral papers, among, 1 piece in a foreign language literature; By entering the two etymology of "Chinese piano music" and "aesthetics", The data of 202 journals and doctoral papers; With "research on the Chinese traditional music theory" as the etymology, There are 171 data in journals and master and doctoral papers, among, 8 foreign documents; With "Chinese style" and "Chinese piano music creation", "Aesthetics" and "Chinese piano music creation", 70 journals and 22 papers respectively, A total of 92 articles; among, 1 foreign literature each; With "Chinese piano music performance" and "Chinese style", "Chinese piano music performance" and "aesthetics" as the two groups of CNKI search etymology, There are 36 journals and 34 master and doctoral papers, respectively, A total of 70 articles; among, 1 foreign literature each; By inputting "Chinese music" and "Chinese discourse", Two groups of etymology, "Chinese piano music" and "Chinese discourse", 52 and 6 papers, respectively, A total of 58 articles; To be clear, During the statistical process, There is the phenomenon of overlapping and overlapping in the research fields, If some papers will be the piano music creation and performance to do a comprehensive research, Some papers combine creation or performance with traditional aesthetics, And so on, Due to the large number of research papers, And it does not affect the overall study of the paper, Therefore, it did not do a more detailed arrangement.

From the statistical data in the table, we can see that in terms of the number of papers, the research results on the "Chinese style" of Chinese piano music are the most fruitful, indicating that the academic circle keeps paying attention to the "Chinese style" of Chinese piano music, which has become one of the hot research perspectives. The smallest proportion is the research on the construction of "Chinese discourse" in Chinese music. It can be seen that the research on "Chinese discourse" of Chinese music is still very weak, and the

research results on "Chinese discourse" of Chinese piano music are even scarce, which has not attracted widespread attention from academic circles.

Limited to space, this paper could not include all research results, so only for theoretical, academic works and music core journals, such as: "music research", "Chinese music", "Chinese musicology", "the journal of the central academy of music," music art ", " yellow bell ", " symphony ", " the "music" has an important influence in some research results to make a brief review.

Research on Chinese and Western aesthetics

In the study of Chinese and Western aesthetics, many scholars give different observations and interpretations from different perspectives and different perspectives. The main theoretical achievements and academic views are shown as follows:

Table 2. Summary table of Chinese and Western aesthetic studies among all scholars

Representative Scholar (year)	Main theoretical achievements and academic views
Zhu Guangqian (1963)	Book with materialism and idealism in the history of the two aesthetic thought formation and development in the process of evolution and struggle as the main line, to the European since ancient Greece and Rome aesthetic important works do overview, trying to be able to clarify the western aesthetic nature about beauty, typical characters, image thinking and creative method of basic aesthetic theory problem;
Zong Baihua (1981)	The monograph embodies Mr.Zong's deep understanding and unique insights into beauty. In the narrative way of the middle mean unique to Chinese culture, he put "reality and virtual" in the aesthetics of Confucius and Mengs represented by "reality" and the old and Zhuang aesthetics represented by "virtual", revealing the complementary relationship between the two. He thinks: in works of art, "virtual" is a kind of not intuitive feeling of emotion, but around the real people or scene is shown incisively and vividly, then the "real" is endowed with wonderful emotion and appears complete, already is no longer the original scenery itself, it is the reality of art constitutes the unique beauty of Chinese classical art, the realm is produced.
Li Zehou and Liu Gangji (1984)	This paper makes an in-depth analysis and interpretation of some basic concepts, categories, propositions, evolution, and development laws of Chinese aesthetics, and points out that the most difficult, complicated, and important link is the most critical in the study of the history of Chinese aesthetics.

Table 2. Summary Table of Chinese and Western Aesthetic Studies of Various Scholars (continued)

Representative Scholar (year)	Main theoretical achievements and academic views
Ye Lang (1985))	The monograph studies and explores some essential characteristics and development laws of the Chinese aesthetic system, which guides for us to understand and grasp the category system of Chinese aesthetics. In addition, also put forward some new ideas of theoretical foresight, such as Mr. Ye Lang thinks: Lao tze aesthetics of the most important category should be "tao" - "gas" - "like" the three categories interconnected and form a category of collection, we should start from the three interconnected category study Lao tze aesthetics because this is the Chinese classical aesthetics a series of aesthetic concept and proposition.
Zong baihua (1987, 1994)	Mr.A realized that the artistic conception of Chinese art focuses on "tong". In the different art forms of Chinese poetry, literature, painting, sculpture, opera, and music, there is a common artistic spirit, a common artistic conception of time and space. In Mr.Zong's eyes, the artistic conception and realm of Chinese art are the rhythm of living life.
Zhang Hao (1996)	Monograph with a large view of traditional culture, innovative adopts the method of cultural reduction, through historical reduction, aesthetic reduction,

and cultural reduction in three levels, sorting, mining, induction, summarize the essence of the Chinese basis of aesthetic category, build a three-dimensional, open, unique traditional aesthetic category system with Chinese characteristics, and think the Chinese aesthetic category system is a dynamic development, rich vitality of the theoretical system. The monograph discusses how to find a way to integrate Chinese aesthetics with Chinese traditional culture through aesthetic interpretation. The book emphasizes the important role of cultural vision in the study of traditional aesthetics. Because as an important part of a culture, nature is associated with a specific culture. Only by extending our tentacles into the traditional culture, can we find the real growth point of aesthetic development.

Liu Chenghua (2002) The professor's broad view of the study of Chinese traditional music occupies an important position in the academic circle. Respectively from the perspective of history and culture and life rhythm unique research, using the method of comparison between Chinese and western music, Chinese music in its rooted cultural ecological environment, based on the connotation of the aesthetic characteristics of Chinese music, Chinese musical timbre connotation, the composition of Chinese music rhyme conducted extensive and in-depth research. According to Liu Chenghua (2002), the different characteristics and fundamental differences between Chinese and Western music aesthetics can only be found in the root of culture.

Zhongde Tsai (2003) The monograph points out that a complete and self-contained aesthetic history should also be a long development history of an aesthetic proposition, category from the origin, formation, continuous integration, evolution to maturity, and cannot be separated from traditional culture. "Confucianism and Taoism" is the origin and foundation of Chinese traditional culture, and the Chinese artistic spirit is deeply contained in the peaceful and deep, quiet and warm, sentimental and generous temperament and temperament. Such as "and" as the core category of Chinese traditional aesthetics, is Confucianism "and different, but not miscellaneous" nature, fully embodies Confucianism in the aesthetic pursuit of some tacit understanding and understanding, "based on the spirit of Chinese music aesthetics is formed based on this" (cheng, 2014). In addition, the monograph makes a comprehensive, detailed, and concise interpretation of the performance aesthetics and its aesthetic propositions involved in The Xishan Music, which is of great significance and far-reaching influence for the study of later and even modern Chinese traditional music aesthetics and provides a lot of reference and guidance for the study of "discourse" of traditional music performance aesthetics.

Table

Table 2. Summary Table of Chinese and Western Aesthetic Studies of Various Scholars (continued)

Representative Scholar (year)	Main theoretical achievements and academic views
Liu Chenghua (2004)	The monograph says: " If explaining Chinese music fails to profoundly reveal and explain what this unique beauty is, then you will not interpret Chinese music in the true sense, so it cannot go deep into the hearts of Chinese audiences

	and resonate."And points out the importance of aesthetic interpretation for Chinese music research.	
Zhang Fang (2005)	The monograph studies the traceability of the basic category of "virtual" and "reality" in traditional aesthetics.	
Wang Zhenfu et al. (2006)	The monograph makes a systematic and in-depth study of the category of Chinese aesthetics with the principle of prioritizing history and returning to the text. Mr.Wang put forward that the root of the traditional Chinese aesthetic category lies in the "qi" in the anthropological sense, "tao" in the philosophical sense, and "elephant" in the artistic sense. It is the close interweaving, interpenetration, and mutual penetration of the traditional aesthetic categories, formed as the origin, core, and base of Chinese aesthetic categories, which jointly build the grand theoretical building of the history of Chinese traditional aesthetic categories.	
Chen Wangheng (2007)	At the beginning of the monograph, the Chinese classical aesthetic system is divided into four systems: "image", "taste" and "wonderful" as the basic category and the unity of "truth, good and beautiful", including aesthetic ontology, aesthetic experience theory, criticism of aesthetic quality, and artistic creation theory. Mr.Chen found a unique way to explore the problem of image creation, and pointed out that in Chinese aesthetics, the existing way of "Tao" is "image", and the fundamental way of "tao" is "taste" image ". The core of Chinese aesthetics should be the image, and the realm is the highest level of an image. In addition, Chen Zhu also attaches great importance to the relationship between aesthetics and art. He put forward that Western aesthetics depends more on philosophy and religion, while Chinese aesthetics is more dependent on art, but it does not ignore the connection between aesthetics and philosophy and religion.	
Zhu Liyuan (2009)	The monograph breaks through the paradigm of traditional aesthetics history, restores the internal correlation between aesthetics, philosophy, history, and other cultural factors, and re-examines and combs the development of western aesthetics with the paradigm of ideological history. It can be said that it is a transcendence of the "aesthetic routine" of the writing of the history of aesthetics.	
Wan Zhiquan (2010)	The monograph focuses on the core problem of the "ancient Chinese aesthetic ideal".	

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ce: collation of this study

It is worth noting that in recent years, as an important branch of Chinese traditional music, music performance's aesthetic field, with the deepening of the theory of music aesthetics, has made substantial progress. Studies in this field include Xiu Hailin (2004), Gong Nili (2013), etc., among which there are many classical discussions of Chinese traditional music performance aesthetics. Zhang (2005) chapter 11 about "the Chinese traditional music performance aesthetics" project, the Chinese traditional music performance aesthetic thought development track the system summary: Yang Yihe the principle and application of music performance art using western music performance aesthetic thinking concept, the traditional Chinese traditional music performance aesthetic thought and the combination of music performance art practice law depth exploration.

Aesthetic thought history is trying to grasp the ideological and cultural development is closely related to aesthetics, the above aesthetic works in the study of aesthetics obscure mapping and never stop search process, presents the contemporary vision of the traditional aesthetic field of multi-angle overall expansion, fully demonstrates the richness, openness, and ductility of aesthetic research. Scholars' discussion and discussion of many issues are fully explained with quite solid and powerful materials and repeatedly demonstrated, showing their rigorous academic attitude and solid theoretical skills.

In addition to the above main works, the relevant academic papers are also extremely rich. Due to the limited space, only some research results with strong academic nature, and unique insights which are closely combined with this paper are selected:

Liu Chenghua (2001,2010,2014) several papers advocate that the study of Traditional Chinese traditional music should find a reasonable and modern interpretation method from cultural science, explore the regularity based on interpretation, and reveal its internal tension. At the same time, it also points out that the construction of "Chinese traditional aesthetics" should draw lessons from the theoretical logic of western aesthetic research.

besides, Liu Chenghua (2021), Han Xunguo (2005), Zheng Yanli (2006), Luo Yifeng (1995), Fengshan (1999), Du Gang (2015), Guan Jianhua (2013), Han Jing (2015), Fan Weiping (2014), Zhao Wenyi (2021), Liu Shutong (2012) in the traditional aesthetics "harmony", "taste", "sound," harmony ", " implicit ", and try to grasp the central characteristics of traditional music, Exploring the possibilities of the humanistic interpretation of traditional music, And then enrich the discourse expression space of traditional music theory.

Sun Xingqun (2015) made a comprehensive and systematic review of the aesthetic thoughts of Le Ji. Fan Lizhi (2004), Yang Xianzhong (2008), Kong Wenwen (2009), wang Tong (2013) and several articles, the Chinese piano music in traditional aesthetics, the "nature and humanity""reality""artistically vivid" aesthetic important proposition embodiment, fully reflects the traditional aesthetic unique thinking in Chinese piano music mapping, truly practice the "modern thinking and traditional aesthetics". These studies have opened up new knowledge of the original thought of Chinese music aesthetics and provided significant research ideas and important theoretical support for this paper to infiltrate the aesthetic research into the practice of Chinese piano music creation and performance, and then construct the "Chinese discourse" system.

Research on the theory of the Chinese traditional music

Many scholars are in " traditional music is the essence and foundation of the national music culture."This point of view has formed a consensus.

Table 3 Summary table of Chinese traditional music theory

Representative Scholar (year)	Main research results and academic views
Qiao Jianzhong, Han Zhong'en, and Luo Qin (2009)	The fundamental difference between traditional music and new music is the style characteristics and the form of expression taken in the work, and it is not referring to the order of creation time. We must arrange, interpret and connect the inherent cultural essence of our country, and carry it forward in the harmony between China and the West.
Yuan Jingfang (2000)	The monograph defines the connotation of "Chinese traditional music": that is, the music created by the Chinese people using the inherent methods and the inherent forms of their nation. It includes not only the ancient works produced in history and handed down from generation to generation but also the musical works created by the contemporary Chinese people in the inherent form of their nation. These three "inherent" basically cover the form, method, and morphological characteristics of music, which cover the emergence and existence of music art, forming the connotation of Chinese traditional music with "inherent" as the essential feature. The "inherent" here only refers to the inherent concept of time, rather than the "inherent" in the form and method, thus showing the characteristics of "space-time" and "diachronic".
Tian Yaonong (2014)	The monograph deeply analyzes and demonstrates the basic structure of Chinese music, and puts forward some unique views on the connotation of "sound", "sound", "sound", big sound "and" sound without sorrow music ", and makes a new interpretation.
Liu Yongfu (2011)	This paper presents different views on the "inherent" theory of traditional music. It is pointed out that music art has absolute variability and relative stability in its development process. In the formation and development process of any country or nation, the music of any school or any kind of music will show the regularity of "variability" beyond "stability". Among them, "stability" is only relative, local, superficial, and temporary, while "variation" is absolute, comprehensive, essential, and eternal.
Du Yaxiong (2018)	In the article, it is clearly stated that "Chinese music theory" does not refer to the current popular music theories in China, nor the corresponding academic theories produced by Chinese people after the study of foreign music theory, but only refers to the theory of "traditional Chinese music". Because Chinese traditional music is the foundation of our Chinese nation, is the source of

Representative Scholar (year)	Main research results and academic views
Du Yaxiong (2019)	<p>Chinese national music to the development and strong support."</p> <p>From the "surface" to the "deep" structure of Chinese music theory, he makes a traceable, comprehensive, and systematic analysis and explanation of the deep connotation of "sound, sound, law, palace, tune, tune, section, beat, board, eye and spectrum" of Chinese music theory.</p>

Source: collation of this study

besides, Xiang Yang (2006, 2020), Fan Zuyin (2017), Wang Yaohua (2010), Dai fang (2008), Duan Qiaosheng and Mi Ruiling (2006), Fu Limin (2015), Feng Guangyu (1992), Shi Yong (2018), Chen Qihe (2012), Wang Yaohua (2015), Du Yaxiong (2017), Zhang Wei (2015), Yang Shanwu (2019), Happy (1999) and other papers, From different perspectives of cultural cognition, research path, and theoretical traceability, In the all-round and multi-angle analysis and demonstration of Chinese traditional music historical materials, This paper discusses the inheritance and development of the Chinese traditional music in depth.

The above works and academic papers show the innovative research achievements of Chinese traditional music, promote the academic thinking of this research, and provide many important references and theoretical support for the research on music form and content, music creation, and performance.

Research on Chinese Music and Discourse Construction

In 2017-2019 three consecutive terms of Chinese music theory discourse system seminars, on how to use the Chinese nation's unique traditional music culture and music characteristics, aesthetic characteristics of Chinese music theory discourse system for all-round, multi-angle combing and reflection, for the construction of Chinese music discourse theory system provides extremely important theoretical guidance and path guidance. However, due to the short time, the system has not yet been formed, and the relevant theoretical works are also relatively scarce.

ShiXu (2014) initiative points out the importance of "Chinese discourse" analysis and research: in western monopoly, east imbalance aphasia special era background, academic and cultural resources in Chinese discourse research paradigm under the framework of reconstruction, for contemporary Chinese discourse theory rooted local, around the world, actively explore methods and solve the path is of great significance. This paper actively explores the basis and conditions of constructing contemporary Chinese discourse theory and method, the concept, theory, and method of traditional Chinese linguistic communication, the relationship between Chinese discourse and international discourse, and the problems of entering the world. This pioneering study of "Chinese discourse" provides an important reference for the penetration and expansion of Chinese discourse in various contemporary fields, which is very precious.

At the first Academic Seminar on the Chinese Music Theory discourse System (Creation Theory), the participating experts discussed the connotation and construction of the topic system of Chinese music theory from multiple disciplines and perspectives. This paper actively discusses the many problems of constructing the system of Chinese music discourse theory. From the perspective of cultural time and space, Xiang Yang put forward that the "system" should be combined from both theory and practice, and should be rationally arranged and constructed from the aspects of music ontology, creation theory, performing art theory, and other aspects. (Guo Kejian and Zhang Yue, 2018)

In the second Symposium on Chinese Music Theory discourse System (Performance Theory), the participating experts discussed six topics, such as "the deep connotation of the discourse of Chinese music performance theory, the history and aesthetics of Chinese music performance, and the relationship between music performance and creation". The aim is to form an accurate cognition of the discourse system of traditional music performance theory from the theoretical discussion of "common understanding and personalized interpretation" of different kinds of performance theories from the multidisciplinary perspective. Zhao Tarim believes that the resources of music practice experience and historical literature should be taken as the resources for building the theoretical discourse system of Chinese music performance. Xiang Yang believes that we should attach importance to grasping the historical depth and constructing a comprehensive discourse system of the Chinese traditional music performance theory on the whole. Luo Yifeng believes that only with a deep understanding of the theoretical discourse with unique Chinese cultural characteristics can the traditional music-theoretical discourse be activated. (Hu Bin, 2019)

At the third Symposium on Chinese Music Discourse Theory System (Creation Theory), the participating experts reached a consensus on constructing the discourse system of Chinese music creation theory "based on tradition". Emphasize the "Chinese music creation theory discourse system" build the core problem, namely the "China" attribute, think "creative theory discourse system", should be a composer too, Chinese traditional music deep cultural connotation of mining, find the direction, clear objectives, in clarifying the basis of culture gene, the theory discourse source, targeted, build, a unique Chinese traditional culture aesthetic characteristics of

creative discourse theory system. (Ji Degang, 2020) Related academic papers and academic views are shown as follows (Table 4):

Table 4 Summary of academic views of scholars on the discourse construction of Chinese music theory

Representative Scholar (year)	Main academic views
Xie Jiaying (2005)	We need to construct a reasonable discourse framework to explore the spiritual pursuit of artistic creation. The construction of this framework should not only pay attention to and emphasize the connotation of the artist's personality and temperament but also examine it in the broad space of cultural history and social history. Only in a specific cultural context, can we have a clearer understanding and grasp of the artists' aesthetic thoughts, and can we clarify the true meaning of their creative practice? As a special cultural interpretation activity, music creation and performance practice are the results of the dialogue, collision, and integration of specific music culture and professional practice context.
Yang Shanwu (2018)	The characteristics and laws in music need to be found in the analysis and research of ontology. The process of discourse construction is the process of continuous exploration, accumulation, and understanding of the essential characteristics and laws of Chinese traditional music humanism.
Yang Heping (2018)	The unique theoretical character and unique practical value of Chinese traditional music performance aesthetics are the abstract existence of the skills accumulated under the practice of Chinese traditional music performance artists, and the theoretical paradigm of Chinese traditional music performance practice provides the practical basis for the living inheritance of Chinese traditional music performance. The construction of the Chinese traditional music performance aesthetic theory discourse system needs in the Chinese traditional music performance skills, aesthetic consciousness, artistic style of deepening cognition, in the Chinese traditional aesthetic theory and music performance practice of two-way propulsion, reveal the aesthetic essence of the Chinese traditional music performance art and spiritual characteristics.
Wang Ci Zhao (2018)	The accurate use of concepts is an important part of language expression and an important part of the construction of the discourse system. The discourse system of music art is a multi-level and diversified whole, which should be combined with macro, medium, and micro levels to develop a comprehensive theoretical elaboration from different levels. Macro elaboration refers to the multiple disciplines of music elaboration, including aesthetics, culture, history, anthropology, sociology, and other disciplines; medium exposition refers to the elaboration of music elements and their relations, including the selection of melody and rhythm, structure arrangement of multi-voice application; micro exposition refers to the theoretical elaboration of music phenomena, involving specific musicians, music works, concerts and music activities.
Xiang Yang (2019)	From the perspective of ritual music, it is pointed out that the construction of the theoretical discourse system of Chinese music performance theory needs to rely on relevant literature to identify the existence of the current traditional music, and comprehensively consider the music performance and acceptance psychology from multiple perspectives.
Wang Xuqing (2020)	Looking down from the macro context, music is a special expression mode of language and discourse with sound as the carrier. In the same musical style of the same era, even in the music creation of different times and different cultural backgrounds of hui, there are often some common musical language patterns and then condensed into a common musical language expression of cultural genes. This just shows that the development of the seemingly diverse music art lies in the profound cultural tradition, which provides a very broad and rich soil and a greater possibility for us to find a common and universal

"musical language expression mode".

Table 4 Complete Table of Academic View of Chinese Music and DisConstruction by Scholars (continued)

Representative Scholar (year)	Main academic views
Liu Nan, Yang Le With Dong Lei (2021)	In the process of summarizing the historical development of Chinese traditional music and digging into the deep cultural connotation of Chinese traditional music, we should explore the basic law that should be followed in constructing a unique creation theory discourse system in Chinese music creation.

Source: collation of this study

besides, Xiang Yang (2020), Xiao Mei (2020), Dai Shuangrong (2014), Wang Xuqing (2020), Du Yaxiong (2019), Xie Jiaying (2004), Guan Jianhua (2018), Yang Shanwu (2019), Xiao Mei (2016), Wang Ci Zhao (2018), Zhu Yujiang (2020), Wang Xu (2018), Wang Zhou and Wang Yaohua (2018), Lin Gufang (1994), Wu Xiaona and Chen Yong (2001), Chen Yaxian (2019), Wang Yaohua (2012), Ma Yuanrui (2018), Ding Hao, Lu Jinjing (2018), Wang Anchao (2012) and other research results respectively studied and discussed the construction of traditional music discourse system from linguistics, music type learning, anthropology, and other perspectives, The research in this field presents the characteristics of richness, deep extension, and ductility, It provides a window for the construction of Chinese piano music "Chinese discourse".

Conclusion

Not only because of dozens of works and nearly a thousand journals and master and doctoral papers, but more importantly, its huge research system, interdisciplinary disciplines, rich research content, and in-depth analysis and discussion, the research results show great diversity and openness. In particular, those research results combined with traditional aesthetics, culture, hermeneutics, and other disciplines are more diverse from various angles and have unique insights. Such diverse and rich theoretical research results provide a great extension space for the research of this paper.

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